

PROSPECTS FOR USING THE BEST FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN EFFICIENT HEALTH STAFF MANAGEMENT

Umarov Botirjon Akhmadaliyevich

Associate professor of Medicine faculty at "Alfraganus"

University.botirumarov64@gmail.com

Ynusova Shohsanam Ulugbekovna

AxmadaliyevaEzoza Botirirovna

Tashkent Dental Institute Department of orthodontics, masters' degree,
2nd semester

shohsanam2931@mail.ru ezoza2000@mail.ru

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the opinions of foreign and our republican scientists on the introduction of a modern system of effective management of healthcare workers. It also covers evolutionary approaches to the effective management of field staff and the nature of their stages, the challenges of implementing a modern and efficient healthcare management system and ways to solve them.

Introduction. In the effective management of health care workers, modern management skills, that is, more efficient resource management, health care workers, ensuring their efficient operation and predicting the quality of health services provided to the population through their effective performance, it is time to improve the processes for their further improvement in industries. From this point of view, the application of foreign experience of modern and effective management is a choice that requires unique high art and skill, making a decision based on this choice and monitoring its implementation is one of the most important tasks.

Under the current socio-economic reforms in our republic, along with the efficient use of financial, economic and material resources, it is necessary to increase the role of industry workers. To do this, health care leaders must recognize that the workers in each industry are the main value of this health system in the process of modern and effective management of it. By the end of the 20th century, institutions and organizations managed to become a universal form of human life and acquired a number of characteristics, such as purposefulness, functioning and development, a regulated organizational structure, a separate culture, constant communication with the external environment, and the use of various resources. The

combination of these characteristics is unique to each industry institution and organization in which human resources are central.

A modern and efficient personnel management system consists of the selection and maintenance of the necessary personnel for institutions and organizations of the industry, their professional training, the correct assessment of the activities and actions of each employee of the industry, and increasing their efficiency. Moreover, as a result of the formation of the digital economy and the development of innovations in the republic, the formation of modern healthcare institutions and organizations consisting of highly qualified personnel remains a requirement of the modern era.

In his address to the "OliyMajlis", President Sh.M. Mirziyoev repeatedly touched upon the personnel issue and expressed the following opinions: "As the wise men of the East said, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, the greatest poverty is ignorance"! Therefore, for all of us, the acquisition of modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a constant vital need. To achieve progress, we need and need to master digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension" (1). In the context of the digitalization of the economy of Uzbekistan and the development of advanced innovative technologies, bringing complex management processes to the micro level requires the adaptation of all elements in the organization of the emerging management system. Therefore, there is a need to develop new methods and forms for evaluating the activities of sectoral institutions and organizations, including new methods for analyzing labor relations and indicators. In the current era of high globalization, the wrong selection of personnel, in turn, leads to large losses for industry institutions and organizations. It is important for heads of sectoral institutions and organizations or specialists in the field who directly work with personnel (*personnel*) to take into account when selecting personnel - to know not what a person did before, but what he can do now. In this sense, the issue of researching technologies used in various companies of the world in the process of selecting and hiring personnel, effectively managing them and effectively using their potential, studying the directions of their use in our national economy remains relevant.

Analysis of the literature on the topic. Problems of personnel management S. Marr, R.L. Daft(2), The works of foreign scientists, such as KamingM.A.(3), are devoted to this. Along with general issues of their management, various areas related to human resource management were considered. In solving various problems related to personnel management, CIS scientists L.D. Kartashova(4), and others. Features of solving these problems in Uzbekistan D.A. Asadov(5), B.M. Mamatkulov(6), K.Kh. Abdurakhmonov(7), D.N. Rakhimova(8), and other scientists. Their works highlight general theoretical and some methodological issues of personnel management.

It should be noted that work in today's rapidly changing market conditions requires a new look at the problem of effective personnel management. A developed competitive environment, in turn, is important in determining the competitiveness of industry workers, requiring constant improvement of their skills. Currently, management is considered in the literature as the implementation of modern management functions. Therefore, the following

management rule has been adopted: effective management is the processes of planning, externalization, motivation and control necessary to determine and achieve the goals of sectoral institutions and organizations.

The literature also notes that in order to manage employees, it is necessary to know what a person's behavior depends on, what is based on it in his life. Behavior, activities and actions of a person are understandable and aimed at achieving the goal. Material and spiritual needs are the forces that motivate action. However, not all human actions are aimed at satisfying their needs. For example, a worker does not create certain material and spiritual goods only for his own consumption. There are a number of direct links between the needs of employees and their behavior. It is interest, desire, passion. Under certain circumstances, they become the driving force behind human behavior. When a stimulus leads to a decision to act, the decision leads to action.

Research methodology. The methodological basis of the study is the legal documents in the field of personnel management and regular training and development, in particular the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4749 (9), Message of the President of the Republic Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoyevOliyMajlis(1), decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2017 No. 795 "On further improvement of the main positions of employees and classification of employees". In addition, based on the requirements set forth in these decrees and resolutions, to ensure competitiveness in the effective management of employees by regularly improving their qualifications, to continue reforms aimed at introducing modern and effective management principles and concepts, effective employee management into management systems and KPI (*Key Performance*) systems. Indicators) when evaluating their activities, proposals and recommendations on the main directions and the corresponding procedural approach, comparative systemic, analysis and synthesis, methods of induction and deduction are widely used.

Analysis and results. In the process of researching the category of modern and effective employee management in the analysis of documents related to the labor legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it became known that employees of sectoral institutions and organizations are divided into several categories according to the system of descriptions and indicators of the content of work and they are given separate definitions. According to it, in state enterprises, sectoral institutions and organizations, economic management bodies, as well as statutory bodies created by resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers on the basis of the "Classification of the main positions and occupations of employees" (10,11), approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 795, employees of sectoral institutions and organizations, in whose capital the state share is more than 50 percent, are divided into the following categories according to the system of descriptions and indicators of the content of work.

Description of employees according to the system of descriptions and indicators of the content of labor.

Table 1.

Category of employees in the management system
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Management system employees	Production staff	Technical staff	Service staff
<p>These are employees who perform effective management functions, manage employees, develop and make the necessary decisions, plan, control and regulate the activities of industry institutions and organizations, prepare information for making the necessary decisions. The management apparatus ensures the fulfillment of the necessary organizational and technical conditions, assigned functions and production programs to achieve the goals and objectives set by industry institutions and organizations. Management personnel, in turn, is divided into managers and specialists of management personnel.</p>	<p>These are employees who are directly involved in the production of the main products of industry institutions and organizations, as well as in the production of additional products specified in the production program. The production staff includes specialists who are directly involved in the production process.</p>	<p>This function includes employees who provide technical support for the activities of the management team and carry out production and technological processes (<i>publishing and reproduction, archival, library work, delivery of documents and other activities</i>).</p>	<p>These functions include the protection and maintenance of buildings and territories, transport services for the management, other services for the management and production personnel of industry institutions and organizations, including workers of social services. Service workers also include professional and non-working domestic service workers.</p>

On the basis of our study, we consider it appropriate to dwell on the features of the personnel management process in industry-specific institutions and organizations. At the same time, we can see the specific features of the personnel management process in the following: Firstly, personnel management includes administrative tasks necessary to control employees of industry institutions and organizations, allowing the use of any methods and techniques that have a positive value. impact on work efficiency; Secondly, there are no sectoral institutions and organizations without employees, and without qualified personnel, sectoral institutions and organizations cannot achieve their goals. Therefore, without effective management of employees, it is impossible to direct them to their activities; Thirdly, in modern management, the "whiplash" management system is not effectively evaluated in terms of its impact on employees. Because this method does not allow to retain modern and talented personnel in sectoral institutions and organizations for a long time. causes a shortage of personnel in sectoral institutions and organizations and leads to a decrease in work efficiency; Fourthly, personnel management is organized on the basis of achieving efficiency and fairness. If one of them is missing, this process cannot be completed successfully. Through effective management of employees, it is possible to unite all employees of sectoral

institutions and organizations, regardless of their position, social origin and gender, to increase labor productivity in sectoral institutions and organizations. This allows each employee to contribute not only as an employee of sectoral institutions and organizations, but also as a person with his selfless work. It ensures the stability of sectoral institutions and organizations as a mechanism for achieving efficiency with a fair organization of labor.

In world practice, there are mainly two American and Japanese approaches to the formation of personnel management systems. Both approaches are aimed at activating human resources, continuous technological improvement, strategic focus on a large number of types of services and goods, delegation or transfer of rights, powers and responsibilities for making a number of important decisions to lower levels of production. control. Also, these approaches are aimed at the development and implementation of long-term strategic plans for the development of sectoral institutions and organizations (12,13). Also, the American approach to the formation of a personnel management system in the United States is based on the principle of individuality. When selecting employees, American corporations prefer individuals who are bright, charismatic, active and creative in solving tasks and developing ideas, who are capable of a non-standard approach and are able to achieve the expected results. In Japan, the practice of managerial decision-making surprises many foreign managers. Decision-making is carried out collectively, and the general decision is made on the basis of consensus. They discuss the proposed solution until there is a general agreement within the institutions and the organization, and after reaching a consensus, they accept it. The Ringi System, NENKO and Lifetime Employment systems are widely used in Japan. These systems, widely used in Japan, emphasize the importance of teamwork and human interaction. One of the main factors that made the Japanese managementsystem famous in the world is the high level of competence in working with people.

- The need for unification and formalization in the application of modern and effective methods of field personnel management
- Existence of need for long-term and strategic planning of field workers.
- Availability of specific functions in the modern and efficient management of field workers.
- Increase attention to the use of information and communication technologies in the modern and efficient management of field workers.

Comparative table of American and Japanese models of personnel management
Table 2.

Controldirection	Collective	Individual
1. Management structure.	1. Non-standard, flexibility. 2.	1. Fixed mode.
2. Making a decision.	Collective and informal.	2. Individual and official.
3. Relations with subordinates.	3. Versatility is a priority for	3. The narrow focus on
4. Evaluation of labor and wages.	team results.	personal results depends on
5. Personnel training.	4. Team.	individual and personal
6. Responsibility and control.	5. Depends on seniority or age.	results.
7. Promotion.	6. "Soft", informal.	4. "Strict", official post from
8. Development.	7. Gradually, step by step.	the bottom up.
9. General principle of	8. Upward service life, long	5. Negotiable, agreement
	term.	

management.		
10. Set and design.		

Based on *Table 2*, our research shows that while industry institutions, organizational interests, and the business environment are considered important in the US, Japanese corporations succeed by focusing more on employees and taking into account their interests. In addition, while American management is oriented towards individualism and competition, it is not clear whether team spirit and human attitude prevail in Japan. In our opinion, one of the main factors that glorified the Japanese management system in the world is a high level of competence in working with people. Also, Russian economists O. Kolesnikova and A. Donetsk residents study the features of personnel management, focusing on large companies. According to research by scientists, modern and effective personnel management in large companies includes the following features (14,15).

The basis of expected results in the effective management of employees.

Table 3

Expected results with effective management of employees in industry institutions and organizations				
Increasing the capabilities of employees	the of	Reducing skill gaps among employees	Significant improvements in labor productivity	Improving the quality of services across the board

Based on *Table 3*, based on our research, the category of effective personnel management was evaluated. Therefore, in our opinion, the expected results should be achieved with the effective management of workers in field institutions and organizations (*improving the abilities of workers, reducing the shortage of skills among workers, a significant increase in labor productivity performed in the fields, improving the quality of services in each area*) are the goals of effective management of field institutions and organization, and based on the direction, one can say the process of achieving efficiency as a result of the correct distribution, direction and influence of the task by planning, organizing, motivating, coordinating and controlling the work process.

- when selecting, placing and promoting employees in their specialty, it is necessary to comprehensively and objectively assess the level of their professional qualifications, attitude to work, moral qualities, and the results of their activities. It is better to use a selection based on the principles of openness and equality in the assessment of professional activity;
- implementation of the KPI system (*KPI*) in all sectoral institutions and organizations. The system allows you to view the motivationally effective system of remuneration in sectoral institutions and organizations through indicators;
- Strengthen the system of informatization and digitalization in all sectoral institutions and organizations. In conditions when time is rapidly developing, when the digitalization system is included in all areas, it is advisable to introduce a modern innovation system in industry institutions and organizations.

At present, all conditions have been created in Uzbekistan for optimizing the personnel management system based on the experience of developed countries. At the same time, all sectoral institutions and organizations of the country, without resorting to this experience, habitually use outdated methods of personnel management, characteristic of the concept of

personnel management in the old administrative-command economy. Given this, sectoral institutions and organizations of Uzbekistan need to compare and critically study certain foreign experience in the field of effective personnel management systems, accumulated in foreign countries with highly developed economies, and effectively use it in management practice. The study of modern forms and methods of effective management of employees and their use in practice makes it possible to achieve highly effective results in domestic institutions and organizations.

Conclusions and offers. Effective management of employees should be organized on the basis of ensuring efficiency and achieving fairness. If one of these two is missing, this process cannot be completed successfully. Through the effective management of employees, it is possible to increase labor productivity only by uniting an industry institution and an organization to achieve a common goal, regardless of the position, social origin and gender of each employee in industry institutions and organizations. As a result, each worker has the opportunity to contribute not only as a member of industry institutions and organizations, but also as a person with a job that he has done of his own free will. It ensures the stability of sectoral institutions and organization as a mechanism for achieving efficiency through the organization of honest work.

Internal processes related to and directly affecting the sustainability of sectoral institutions and organizations always have priority. As a conclusion, we can say that in order to improve the efficiency of the personnel management system, the following proposals and recommendations were made:

In general, the correct selection and placement of personnel in modern management is an important factor in improving the achievements and status of enterprises, industry institutions and organizations. Especially today, creative approaches, a critical analytical attitude and the creation of favorable conditions for the management team are in demand. Also, in a market economy, the correct and efficient use of factors that affect the effectiveness of personnel management in sectoral institutions and organizations is crucial for improving the efficiency of economic development of sectoral institutions and organizations. All these processes mean further deepening of personnel reforms in Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoyev to the OliyMajlis and the people of Uzbekistan. 21.12.2022. and 24.01.2020. <http://www.press-service.uz>
2. Marr S, Schmidt G. Upravleniepersonelom v usloviyakhsotsialnoyrnochnoyekonomiki. M., 2009.-p. 66.
3. Kaming M.A. Theory and practice of management personnel. - M.: Novosti, 2015.-p.35.
4. Upravleniechelovecheskimiresourcesami: Uchebnik/ L. V. Kartashova. -M.: INFRA-M,2013.
5. D.A. Asadov. Public health and health management. Manual for heads of primary health care facilities. "SANNOF" publishing house. Tashkent-2022.
6. B.B. Mamatkulov. Health management and economics. Textbook. "VORIS" publishing house. Tashkent-2015.

7. Q. Kh. Abdurakhmanov. Personnel management. Textbook. T-"Science and technology". 2008., Labor economy. Textbook.-T: "Labor", 2009
8. D.N. Rakhimova. Upravlenie processami razvitiya I ispolzovaniya trudovo gopotenziala Uzbekistana v usloviyaxoshushestvleniyaradicalnkrmnochnmx reform: Monograph. - T.: TashGTUim. A.R. Beruni, 2000. "Economy and innovative technologies" scientific electronic journal. No. 4, July-August, 2021 4/2021 (No. 00054) <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz> 138
9. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4749 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
10. Resolution No. 795 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2017 "On further improvement of the main positions of employees and classification of workers".
11. N. Mausov Menedzhment person nela klyuchevo ezveno vnutrifirmenn ogoupravleniya//Problemyteoriiipraktikiupravleniya. 2016. No. 6-S.8.
12. R. Marra Personnel management and social market economic conditions//R. Marra, G. Schmidt. 2014.
13. Rakhmanov, T. O., Umarov, B. A., Saydalikhujhaeva, Sh. Kh., &Ibragimkhodjaev, B. (2022). Innovative approach and process management and dentistry. models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research, 2(18), 38-42.
14. Kuliev, O. A., Umarov, B. A., Kamilova, D. N., &Ruzieva, S. Yu. (2022). The role of a fertility doctor and the formation of a healthy image. models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research, 2(18), 43-48.
15. KurambaevYa.B., Umarov B.A., AkramovaL.Yu. "Use of information communication and innovative pedagogical technologies in medical education" Instructional manual. TDSI. Tashkent,2021.